

Idioms in English

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Abstract

An idiom is a phrase that is common to a certain population. It is typically figurative and usually is not understandable based solely on the words within the phrase. A prior understanding of its usage is usually necessary. Idioms are crucial to the progression of language. They function in a manner that, in many cases, literal meanings cannot. Idioms are words or phrases that aren't meant to be taken literally. Webster's New World adds "[It] has a meaning that differs from the literal meaning of its parts taken together." For example, if you say someone has "cold feet," it doesn't mean their toes are actually cold. Rather, it means they're nervous about something.

Key words: reality, backwards, ferocious, pity, juvenile, fabulous, security. Human, keyword, livestock, mezzanine, sensational, famlous

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Отрывок

Идиома – это фраза, которая является общей для определенной группы населения. Обычно это образное выражение, и его обычно невозможно понять, основываясь исключительно на словах внутри фразы. Обычно необходимо предварительное понимание его использования. Идиомы имеют решающее значение для развития языка. Они функционируют так, как во многих случаях буквальное значения не могут. Идиомы – это слова или фразы, которые не следует понимать буквально. В «Новом мире» Вебстера добавляется: «[Он] имеет значение, которое отличается от буквального значения его частей,

взятых вместе». Например, если вы говорите, что у кого-то «холодные ноги», это не значит, что пальцы на ногах на самом деле холодные. Скорее, это означает, что они чем-то нервничают.

Ключевые слова: действительность, задом наперед, свирепый, жалостливый, малолетний, сказочный, безопасность. Человек, ключевое слово, домашний скот, мезонин, сенсационный, знаменитый

Early bird: A person who wakes up and starts their activities early in the morning.

Daylight: The natural light during the day, typically after sunrise and before sunset.

High noon: The exact middle of the day; 12:00 PM. It's often associated with the time for a showdown or decisive confrontation.

Midday: The middle of the day; another term for noon.

Dawn: The time of day when light first appears, before sunrise.

Dusk: The time of day just after sunset, when light is fading.

Daybreak: The time when day first begins; dawn.

Broad daylight: The time of day when it is fully light because the sun is high in the sky, typically associated with the time when it is easiest to see things clearly or when most people are awake and active.

Golden hour: The period of daytime shortly after sunrise or before sunset, during which daylight is redder and softer than when the sun is higher in the sky.

Even though they might sound funny, idioms concisely describe complex feelings and ideas. They often allow you to discuss complex topics without causing offense or awkwardness.

Using them in your speech – or writing – can help you sound more comfortable and natural.

Must-know German idioms to enrich your vocabulary

Here are some of the most popular, helpful, and memorable German idioms to get you started. You'll also get a translation of the idioms in English, so you know exactly what you're saying.

1. Alles hat ein Ende, nur die Wurst hat zwei

Literal translation – Everything has an end; only the sausage has two

English translation – Everything comes to an end

The reference to a sausage may not make logical sense, but it is used to emphasize the first part of the idiom, that all things must come to an end.

Ich habe ein tolles Buch zu Ende gelesen! Ich bin ein bisschen traurig, aber alles hat ein Ende, nur die Wurst hat zwei! – I finished reading a great book! I'm a bit sad, but everything has an end, only the sausage has two!

2. Auf der Leitung stehen

Literal translation – To stand on the line

English translation – To not follow or understand

In the early days of phones, if somebody would stand on the telephone wire it would mean that you couldn't communicate with the other person because nothing you say would get through to them. This is what this idiom means – if you try to explain something to someone, but they can't follow, they're "standing on the line".

Ich habe es dir dreimal erklärt. Du stehst wohl auf der Leitung? – I explained it to you three times. You still don't understand?

3. Da haben wir den Salat

Literal translation – There we have the salad

English translation – We're in trouble now

Did your brother ignore your advice to attach the lid to the smoothie maker before turning it on? Now the kitchen is a mess, or in other words, "there we have the salad".

Da haben wir den Salat. Nun, das ist jetzt dein Problem – We're in a mess here. Well, it's your problem now.

4. Da kannst du Gift drauf nehmen

Literal translation – You can take poison on that

English translation – You can bet on it

This idiom is used to express certainty. It implies that something is true beyond doubt.

Bayern wird dieses Spiel gewinnen. Da kannst du Gift drauf nehmen – Bayern will win this game. You can be sure of it.

5. Da steppt der Bär

Literal translation – The bear is dancing there.

English translation – This party or place is so happening.

If a place is a lot of fun, you'd say, "the bear is dancing there." This has its origins in the days when dancing bears entertained people. Luckily, bears don't do this anymore, but the idiom lives on.

Hast du von Rudy's Party gehört? Bonez MC ist da! Da Steppt Der Bär! – Have you heard about Rudy's party? Bonez MC is there! It's happening there!

6. Das Zünglein an der Waage

Literal translation – The pointer on the scales

English translation – To tip the scale

This is similar to the English expression, to "tip the scale" or "reach a tipping point." When a scale is perfectly balanced, it only takes one small thing to send it one way or the other. Use this expression to describe something that leads to a final decision or result after a long process.

Das Komitee war sich uneins darüber, ob es mit dem Projekt fortfahren sollte. Die Stimme des Vorstandsvorsitzenden war das Zünglein an der Waage – The committee was evenly split about whether to proceed with the project. The chief executive's vote was what tipped the scales.

7. Dumm wie Bohnenstroh

Literal translation – As dumb as a beanstalk.

English translation – As dumb as a rock

This famous German idiom describes someone who is particularly stupid or naive. It implies that the person in question is unable to think for themselves.

Babys sind toll aber sie sind manchmal dumm wie Bohnenstroh – Babies are great, but sometimes they're dumb as rocks.

Break a leg – to wish someone good luck

Cost an arm and a leg – to be very expensive

Bite the bullet – to face a difficult situation bravely

Beat around the bush – to avoid getting to the point in a conversation

Barking up the wrong tree – making a mistake in blaming or accusing someone

A blessing in disguise – a good thing that seems bad at first

Burn the midnight oil – to work hard or study late into the night

Cry over spilt milk – to be upset over something that cannot be changed

A bird in the hand is worth two in the bush – it's better to have something for sure than to take a risk for more

Cat got your tongue – to be speechless

It is difficult for English native speakers to master English idioms, let alone EFL learners because the figurative meanings of English idioms cannot be predicted through an analysis of their individual word meanings. American English is filled with thousands of idioms – expressions for which the meanings cannot be determined based on literal translations of the individual words in the phrase.

Close but no cigar – almost a success but not quite

Cut to the chase – to get to the most important point

Don't judge a book by its cover – not to judge someone or something by appearance only

Easy as pie – very easy

Eat humble pie – to apologize or admit fault

Get cold feet – to lose one's nerve or become too afraid to do something

Get the ball rolling – to start or initiate an action

Give someone the benefit of the doubt – to assume the best of someone

Go against the grain – to do something differently or against the norm

Hit the nail on the head – to get something exactly right.

References

1. Armitage, L., & Burgin, S. (2015). The Pink Poodle, swimming pavilions and Miami Ice. In T. Hundloe, B. McDougall, & C. Page (Eds.), *The Gold Coast transformed: From wilderness to urban ecosystem* (pp. 131–139). CSIRO Publishing.
2. Bond University. (2018, May 2). Tackling social media risks and opportunities at Bond [Video]. YouTube. <https://youtu.be/ZeWW-VnOUUnU>
3. Brand, J. E., Todhunter, S., & Jervis, J. (2017). Digital Australia report 2018. Interactive Games and Entertainment Association. <https://www.igea.net/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/Digital-Australia-2018-DA18-Final-1.pdf>
4. Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation. (n.d.). Overview of gene technology research at CSIRO. <https://www.csiro.au/en/Research/Farming-food/Innovation-and-technology-for-the-future/Gene-technology/Overview>
5. Dellios, R. (2019). Security Landscape. In S. Romaniuk, M. Thapa, & P. Marton (Eds.). *The Palgrave encyclopedia of global security studies*. Palgrave Macmillan. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-74336-3_282-1
6. Fritzon, K., Doley, R., & Hollows, K. (2014). Variations in the offence actions of deliberate firesetters: A cross-national analysis. *International Journal of Offender Therapy and Comparative Criminology*, 58(10), 1150–1165. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0306624X13487524>

7. Stapleton, P. B. (2017). EFT for Teens. Hay House.
8. Taylor, A. (2017). Troubled everyday: The aesthetics of violence and the everyday in European art cinema. Edinburgh University Press.